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PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN THE STRUCTURE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN RUSSIA

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Abstract

The article examines the role of physical culture and sports in the structure of higher education in Russia. The main emphasis is placed on the ongoing modernization of the sphere of physical culture and sports, which has created new conditions for the functioning of sectoral education. Currently, sufficient experience has been accumulated both in the law enforcement practice of legislative changes and in the practice of developing and implementing educational programs at various levels in the academic community, which requires generalization, systematization, comparative analysis with global development trends to solve the problems and inconsistencies that have emerged. The transition to two-level education and training of bachelors and masters entailed a number of consequences that caused a negative reaction from both the labor market and the education system, the controversy over them has not lost its acuteness to date.

Keywords: physical culture, university, education, history, country, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of long-term socio-economic development of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2030 defines the role of physical culture and sports in the development of Russia's human potential.

It is noted that government spending on physical culture and sports for citizens is a cost-effective investment in the development of human potential and improving the quality of life of Russian citizens.

However, the level of development of physical culture and sports does not correspond to the general positive socio-economic transformations in the Russian Federation. In the process of forming a positive attitude towards a healthy lifestyle, which includes an optimal motor regime, the leading role is given to specialists - graduates of universities and physical education departments, who, as the realities of the present time show, do not fully meet social challenges. The resolution of the contradiction between the personal and social need for the realization of the potential of physical culture and the system of traditional higher education in the industry is an important socio-cultural task. It follows that the modernization of the system in the sports industry in order to train specialists who are able to adapt to market conditions is an urgent problem, both from a theoretical and practical point of view.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted on the basis of the dialectical method of analyzing historical phenomena, facts and events that influenced the formation and evolution of professional higher education systems. These processes were studied in self-movement, in development with the establishment of cause-and-effect relationships.

The study was of a complex nature and required a dialectical combination of the development of methodological, psychological-pedagogical, social and methodological aspects of the problem, taking into account modern conditions and achievements of fundamental and applied sciences, affecting the process of professional development and improvement in the system of special physical education.

III. RESULTS

The nature of the professional activity of specialists in the field of physical culture in modern conditions is characterized by variability. The efficiency of labor activity of specialists is determined by the demand for the services they offer, and employers (consumers of services) are ready to pay for them. The quality of services is directly related to the way they are offered and the person who offers and implements them. Consequently, the demand for services in the field of physical culture depends on the level of professionalism and personal qualities of specialists. The effectiveness of promoting the "goods" to the consumer, the professional mobility of a specialist in modern conditions are determined by fundamental preparedness in the natural sciences, humanitarian, special pedagogical blocks of academic disciplines, motor preparedness in basic sports, and social activity. Consequently, the role of the organizational, communicative and motor (multi-disciplinary) components of the professionogram of specialists is increasing. Social processes in the country have changed the nature of the work activity of graduates of higher educational institutions of physical culture, which further exacerbates the contradictions of the subject system of education: between the assimilation of knowledge and skills by students disunited in subjects and the need for their integrated application in real conditions of pedagogical activity is a contradiction that emphasizes the practical aspect of improvement vocational education.

The analysis of staffing problems in the field of physical culture shows the mismatch between social demands, and, consequently, the nature of the professional activity of university graduates, and the nature and direction of professional education of specialists. The structure of the process of higher professional education should evolve taking into account the need to preserve the traditional for domestic universities industry of skills and abilities formation, and the formation of the ability of students (future specialists) to independently acquire the necessary competencies. That is, we should talk about the personal orientation of education. Such an understanding and acceptance of the process of reproduction of specialists in the industry entails a change in strategy, and, consequently, structural transformations in higher professional education.

The concepts of higher professional education in the field of physical culture were formed and improved under the influence of the needs of social life. It developed in two directions: as courses at universities and as an independent industry.

In various countries of the world, many variants of systems for the use of credit units (credit points) in the educational process, which are very diverse, have been created. The most famous of them are European (European Credit Accumulation - ECA), British (Credit Accumulation and Transfer System - CATS), American (US Credit System - USCS). However, in the last 15-20 years, ECTS (European Community Credit Transfer System) has come to the fore. In most universities in Europe, only 10-15% of graduates are trained under the program of trainers, and the rest - to work as teachers and specialists for health-improving physical culture.

A differentiated system for assessing the quality of education encourages students to systematic learning activities. Only regular operational and current pedagogical control, carried out as part of the educational process, allows you to quickly adjust the direction of pedagogical influences and the choice of didactic means by which the solution of the tasks set is achieved. The frequency of pedagogical control is directly related to the success of mastering the program material. Further improvement of higher professional education should be associated, first of all, with an increase in the activity of students in the educational process. This can be achieved by expanding independent work in the educational process, which will contribute to its individualization in the conditions of mass education. The fundamental concept of education in the field of physical culture, based on modern communication capabilities, is the process of self-education. Independent work, as a section of educational activity, should be managed, based on the organizational and methodological support of the process itself and regular monitoring of its results. Students should be more actively involved in the pedagogical process as its organizers and leaders. In the process of educational and methodical classes, where students act as a subject of the pedagogical process, knowledge is integrated, interdisciplinary connections are improved, knowledge acquires practical significance. The conceptual basis of the project of the federal state educational standard of higher professional education is: the desire for an optimal combination of fundamental training at the first level with specialized training at the second level of education, depending on the intended direction of professional activity, is an effective means of resolving the contradiction between the realities of social order and the system of training specialists in higher education institutions of physical culture; observance of the continuity of the traditions of domestic education in the industry in accordance with the content of the state educational standard of the first and second generation; ensuring regional "sensitivity" of education to the dynamics of socio-cultural conditions; preservation of the specifics of domestic education, taking into account the experience of pre-university specialized training of applicants; maintaining the selection of applicants, taking into account preparedness in the chosen sport and training at the first level, taking into account sports specialization; implementation of training within the framework of the theory and methodology of the chosen sport and special disciplines on the principles of establishing interdisciplinary links and implementing a competency-based approach in education; ensuring the profile of training through the variable part of the cycles of academic disciplines; adaptation of foreign experience of activating the regular educational activities of students. The main educational programs of the direction should be formed taking into account: the synergistic potential of individual disciplines and the continuity of profiles at different levels of higher professional education; providing a real opportunity for the student to adjust the educational route, focusing on his professional preferences; ensuring the possibility of mastering several profiles through the continuity of the variable part of the programs in their components - the mandatory and elective parts.

We are living in an era where most of us have a sedentary & stressful life. Every one of us have imagined a life that is full of happiness, success & a good health. We want each day to be more happier than the day before, stress free, and of course the most important in a good state of physical & mental health. A Healthier life is not an easy earn, it comes with a holistic approach considering physical, emotional, social as well as spiritual wellbeing. You can still strive for wellness even if you are experiencing these challenges in your life.

Physical education is necessary for a person at all periods of his life. In childhood and adolescence, they contribute to the harmonious development of the body. In adults, they improve the morphofunctional state, increase efficiency and preserve health. In the elderly, along with this, unfavorable age-related changes are delayed.

Systematic physical education and sports help people of all ages to use their free time most productively, and also contribute to the rejection of such socially and biologically harmful habits as alcohol consumption and smoking.

Abuse of physical activity can bring considerable harm, therefore, when choosing the degree of stress on the body, it is necessary to apply an individual approach.

One of the tasks of physical education in our country is the comprehensive, consistent development of the human body. A person should be strong, agile, hardy at work, healthy, seasoned.

Regular physical exercises or sports increase the activity of metabolic processes, maintain at a high level the mechanisms that carry out the metabolism and energy in the body.

An insufficient amount of motor activity or a violation of the functions of the body with a restriction of motor activity negatively affects the body as a whole. People can live with restricted movements, but this will lead to muscle atrophy, a decrease in bone strength, deterioration of the functional state of the central nervous, respiratory and other systems, a decrease in the tone and vital activity of the body.

IV. CONCLUSION

When forming working curricula in the system of credit units in order to optimize the educational process, it is recommended to provide for the maximum unification of curricula of related areas of training. The implementation of these tasks is most successfully solved with the introduction of a modular system for constructing curricula.

The role of the teacher as a relayer of information has already become obsolete. The time is coming for teachers of "detonators" and consultants (tutors) for the educational activities of students. With such a development of the educational process, the role of motivation, cognitive activity and the ability for independent work of students increases more than ever.

The problem of adaptation of all theoretical disciplines (especially the disciplines of the medical and biological cycle) to the conditions of physical culture activity is becoming extremely topical (mechanical transfer of university curricula to universities of physical culture is practiced). The current system of transferring theoretical knowledge to students is characterized, in our opinion, by certain shortcomings, in particular, it is inappropriate to divide many theoretical (basic) disciplines into two or more parts: general - academic and special - applied. The fragmentation of essentially unified subjects in practical educational work leads to negative phenomena.

Physical culture is an integral part of human life. It occupies a rather important place in people's studies and work. Physical exercises play a significant role in the performance of members of society, which is why knowledge and skills in physical culture should be laid in educational institutions of various levels in stages.

Health is a great blessing, no wonder folk wisdom says: "Health is the head of everything!". Physical activity is one of the most powerful means of preventing diseases, strengthening the body's defenses. No medicine will help a person as much as consistent and systematic physical education.

Recently, there has been a huge increase in the popularity of health-improving physical exercises, people have never been so fond of various forms of health-improving physical education with the whole family as it is happening today.

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ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ КУЛЬТУРА И СПОРТ В СТРУКТУРЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В РОССИИ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается роль физической культуры и спорта в структуре высшего образования в России. Основной акцент сделан на продолжающейся модернизации сферы физической культуры и спорта, которая создала новые условия для функционирования отраслевого образования. В настоящее время накоплен достаточный опыт как в правоприменительной практике законодательных изменений, так и в практике разработки и внедрения образовательных программ различного уровня в академическом сообществе, который требует обобщения, систематизации, сравнительного анализа с мировыми тенденциями развития для решения возникших проблем и несоответствий. Переход на двухуровневое образование и подготовку бакалавров и магистров повлек за собой ряд последствий, которые вызвали негативную реакцию как со стороны рынка труда, так и системы образования, споры вокруг них не утратили своей остроты до настоящего времени.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, вуз, образование, история, страна, общество.

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